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13 **A strip-type boron-doped diamond heater synthesized by chemical vapor deposition for**
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25 **Abstract**

26 **We have developed a high-pressure furnace assembly with a commercially**
27 **available chemical-vapor-deposition (CVD) synthesized boron-doped diamond (BDD)**
28 **heater consisting of four strips for large-volume multi-anvil presses (LVP). This**
29 **assembly successfully generated temperatures to 2990 K at 15 GPa. It also has highly**
30 **reproducible power-temperature relations, enabling us to estimate temperature from**
31 **power reliably. It can be used for experiments above 9 GPa, and is particularly useful**
32 **for synchrotron X-ray experiments because of the X-ray transparency. It is also**
33 **competitive in price. This technique is thus practical in various LVP experiments in the**
34 **diamond-stability field.**

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36 Graphite is a widely used heating element for high-pressure (P) and high-temperature
37 (T) experiments using large-volume presses (LVP) because of the stable generation of very
38 high T and low costs. It is especially useful in synchrotron experiments because of its X-ray
39 transparency. Above 9 GPa, however, it cannot be used due to the transition to diamond, and
40 LaCrO_3 and noble metals are used instead. Due to their X-ray opacity, holes for an X-ray path
41 are made on the heater wall, which causes heating instability, large thermal gradient, and

42 sample deformation. An X-ray transparent heating element usable above 9 GPa has therefore
43 been long-awaited.

44 Boron-doped diamond (BDD) is a candidate to solve the above problems. Although
45 more than 10 years have passed since the first report¹, there are still many problems for
46 practical use. In early studies¹⁻⁴, boron-doped graphite (BDG) instead of BDD was loaded as
47 a precursor because of the much better machinability and lower costs for preparation. At the
48 beginning of heating, a BDG heater generated high T as a graphite heater, and then BDG
49 spontaneously transformed to BDD. A large volume reduction and a drastic resistivity change
50 due to the transformation, however, caused a significant P drop and unstable heating,
51 respectively, which prevented BDG-converted BDD from practical use. Alternatively, Xie et
52 al.^{5,6} proposed methods to use pre-synthesized BDD from BDG at high- P - T (HP-BDD),
53 which can generate T to ~ 4000 K. Consequently, they succeeded in measuring viscosity of
54 silicate melts up to 3250 K and 30 GPa by the in-situ falling sphere method⁶. However, the
55 HP-BDD has to be synthesized at significant high- P - T (15 GPa, 2300 K) and requires
56 considerable effort to be formed a desired shape⁵. These factors hinder its widespread use.

57 Recently, BDD has attracted attention in electrochemistry and electroanalytical
58 applications⁷. Thanks to that, BDD plates manufactured by the chemical-vapour-deposition
59 (CVD) method are commercially available with reasonable prices. Our recent study reported
60 a cylindrical CVD-BDD heater generating similar T to HP-BDD⁸. However, laser cutting of
61 CVD-BDD from a thick plate to a cylindrical shape requires additional costs, and the limited
62 plate thickness (< 1.7 mm) limits the heater dimensions⁸. In this study, we have developed a
63 CVD-BDD heater setting composed of four strips, allowing easy preparation with low cost,
64 and fitting in ordinary LVP assemblies.

65 Figure 1 shows a cross-section of the cell assembly. A polycrystalline CVD-BDD
66 plate synthesized with 2000 ppm B/C ratio in the feeding gas (GH Diamond Tools Co., Ltd.;

67 hereafter referred to as GH) with $3.5 \times 10 \times 0.2$ mm was cut into strips with $1.0 \times 3.5 \times 0.2$ mm by
68 a fiber laser cutter (CombiLine Basic RT, Coherent-ROFIN) (Fig. 2a). A 10-mm Cr-doped
69 MgO octahedron (OM-CR, Mino Yogyo Co., Ltd.) with a square hole with rounded corners
70 was used as a pressure medium (Fig. 2b). A quadratic MgO (TATECERA EMG, Tateho
71 Chemical Industries Co., Ltd.) prism with rounded corners, four side grooves, and holes was
72 used as an insulator and for a support of BDD strips (Fig. 2c). These MgO components were
73 milled using a desk-top modelling machine (MODELA MDX-40A, Roland DG). The BDD
74 strips were easily inserted into the grooves by tweezers. Reagent-grade TiC powder (Alfa
75 Aesar, 99.5%) for electrodes was packed into the stepped holes in the MgO rods (Fig. 2d).
76 Temperature was measured by a $W_{97}Re_3$ - $W_{75}Re_{25}$ thermocouple (TC) based on the calibrated
77 EMF up to 2763 K and its extrapolation to higher T . The TC was insulated from the heater by
78 the MgO prism without any additional component, which reduces risks of TC breaking and
79 chemical reaction between TC and BDD. No glue was used to fix any part to avoid chemical
80 reactions. No ZrO_2 thermal insulator was used to avoid eutectic melting with MgO^5 . The
81 assembly was compressed to 15 GPa using carbide anvils with a 5-mm truncation in the test
82 runs.

83 The T was increased with a 100-K step and reached 2880 K stably with a power (PWR)
84 of 915 W (Run H5158) (Fig. 3). Above this PWR (at time of 2:16 h), however, the T
85 decreased with increasing PWR and with time (Fig. 3). We considered that this phenomenon
86 was a precursor of TC breakage. Then, the TC disconnected at 930 W (2:24 h). As the heater
87 suddenly became unstable at 960 W (2:27 h), we cut the PWR supply.

88 The T generation efficiency was low (2 K/W) at low T (~ 600 K), but increased with
89 increasing T and finally reached 3.2 K/W around 1600 K (Fig. 4), which should reflect T -
90 dependent thermal conductivity (κ) of MgO^9 . We extrapolated the PWR- T relation obtained
91 before the TC breakage to the highest PWR (Fig. 3), which led to 2990 K.

92 To check reproducibility of the PWR- T relations, another run (H5182) was conducted by
93 a different worker using polycrystalline CVD-BDD (B/C = 5000 ppm in gas) from a different
94 supplier (Changsha 3 Better Ultra-hard Materials CO., Ltd.; hereafter referred to as 3B). The
95 PWR- T relations of the two runs were almost identical despite the difference in the highest
96 achieved T (Fig. 4). Therefore, this furnace is reproducible enough to estimate T based on
97 PWR- T relations obtained by separate runs. Note that the resistance of GH's BDD is lower
98 than that of 3B's BDD even though the B/C ratio in gas for GH's BDD is lower. This may be
99 because of different CVD method (GH: hot-filament CVD, 3B: undisclosed)¹⁰. Although to
100 varying degree, the electrically active B concentrations of both BDD can be estimated to be
101 $2\text{--}3 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ from electrical resistivity, which corresponds to hopping conduction close to
102 metallic conduction¹¹. In fact, the resistance of H5182 hardly changed with T , indicating they
103 are close to metallic. It was found that these differences of BDD, however, do not affect the
104 PWR- T relations.

105 We checked the texture and chemical compositions of the recovered sample from H5158
106 using SEM-EDS (Fig. 5). We found a number of small particles of W alloy around the places
107 of the original W-Re wires (Fig. 5b) with BDD fragments (Fig. 5a). No chemical reaction
108 was found between the TiC electrodes and BDD heater. Therefore, TC melting should have
109 caused the heater instability at 2:24 h (~ 2900 K). The TC melting at the apparent T lower
110 than the expected melting T of $\text{W}_{75}\text{Re}_{25}$ at 15 GPa (~ 3700 K) may be due to contamination of
111 surrounding materials. Chemical analysis showed Ti, Cr derived from Cr-doped MgO, and C
112 from BDD in the W alloy, having led to decrease in melting T . This could be a reason for no
113 apparent T increase by PWR increase and spontaneous decrease with time afterwards (Fig. 3).

114 To generate higher T than 3000 K, we have to prevent melting of TC. If due to the
115 contamination, high-purity MgO should be used for pressure media. An ultimate solution is,
116 however, no use of TC. The high reproducibility of the PWR- T relations allows reasonable T

117 estimation based on the PWR. Alternatively, T could be estimated based on volumes of two
118 materials with different thermoelastic properties such as MgO and diamond by *in situ* X-ray
119 diffraction.

120 In addition to the highest achievable T , T uniformity in a sample is important for practical
121 experimental use. We therefore conducted numerical simulations of Joule heating coupled
122 with heat conduction to evaluate T distributions in the cell using commercial software
123 (Autodesk, CFD 2019) (Fig. 6). Values of T -dependent κ , heat capacity, electrical resistivity
124 of materials constituting the cell assembly were taken from literature^{9,12-14}. Although there is
125 some report regarding κ of BDD, the actual κ at high T is still uncertain. For this reason, we
126 used various constant κ from 10 to 200 W/mK with T for BDD. The maximum T difference
127 within a cylindrical sample with a length and diameter of 2 and 1 mm, respectively, was
128 found only 190 K at the center of the cell assembly with BDD κ of 50 W/mK at the central T
129 of 2685 K. If the sample length is reduced to 1 mm, the T difference can be reduced to 70 K.
130 Even though the BDD κ is varied from 10 to 200 W/mK, the results are essentially the same.

131 The present combination of pressure-medium and anvil-truncation sizes allows P
132 generation of 23 GPa. The present furnace can be set in smaller and larger assemblies with
133 minor modification. It can be easily accommodated in a 7-mm pressure medium. A
134 compression of such assemblies using anvils with 3-mm truncations will generate the same T
135 at P to 27 GPa. The strip heaters are, however, unsuitable for smaller cells, for which tubular
136 shapes should be adopted⁸.

137 The cost of four BDD strips is comparable to that of a LaCrO₃ sleeve, which should not
138 be too expensive for many LVP laboratories. Furthermore, linear cutting of BDD plates with
139 a thickness of 0.2 mm is a very easy and inexpensive task for a fiber laser. The present
140 technique is therefore useful in various kinds of LVP experiments.

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148 **Data Availability Statements**

149 The data that supports the findings of this study are available within the article.

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179 **Figures**
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 183 FIG. 1. Cross-sections of the cell assembly. Black arrows indicate the X, Y, and Z axes in the
 184 present coordination system. (a) X-Y plane. The thin and thick dashed lines represent the top
 185 and bottom surfaces of the octahedron, respectively. The magenta dashed dotted line denotes
 186 the X-Z plane shown in FIG. 1b. A dark blue dashed double-dotted line is the cross-section of
 187 the recovered sample shown in FIG. 4. (b) X-Z plane. The yellow dashed dotted line denotes
 188 the X-Y plane shown in FIG. 1a.

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 193 FIG. 2. Photographs of assembly parts. (a) BDD strips. (b) A Cr-doped MgO octahedron
 194 hollowed out by a square with rounded corners. (c) A quadratic prism made of MgO ceramic
 195 with rounded corners, side grooves, and a hole. (d) TiC powder electrodes packed into
 196 stepped-hole in the MgO rod.

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 199 FIG. 3. Heating log (run no. H5158) using GH's BDD. Temperature, apparent PWR,
 200 apparent resistance, current, and voltage against time.

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 204 FIG. 4. A graph of T and apparent resistance against apparent PWR. H5158(GH) and
 205 H5182(3B) denote experiments using GH's and 3B's BDDs, respectively. A black curve
 206 denotes a 4th degree polynomial fit for H5158 using all data except for the data showing the
 207 strange trend (600-750 W). A yellow dashed line denotes a linear fit for H5158 using data
 208 after the strange trend (>750 W).

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FIG. 5. Backscattered-electron images of a recovered sample (H5158). Brightness and contrast were adjusted for MgO (a) and TiC (b). This cross-sectional plane corresponds to the dark blue dashed double-dotted line in Fig. 1a.

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FIG. 6. An example of T distribution of the cell estimated by numerical simulation. Surface boundary conditions for voltage and T set to 10 V and 700 K, respectively. (a) X-Y and (b) X-Z planes correspond to Fig. 1a and 1b, respectively. The black circle and rectangle in (a) and (b), respectively, denote the sample with a height and diameter of 2 and 1 mm, respectively.